

Perception about biological sampling

Veillez remplir le questionnaire ci-dessous.

Merci !

Although no samples will be taken in this project, we would like to know your opinion on sampling procedures (saliva, sweat, hair, blood). Please share your opinion by indicating what you find acceptable.

	Completely unacceptable	Unacceptable	No opinion	Acceptable	Totally acceptable
1) Give a saliva sample using the equipment provided	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2) Give some hairs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3) Give a few clipped nails	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4) Give sweat samples using the equipment provided	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5) Give an urine sample (pee) using the equipment provided	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6) Give a blood sample	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7) Give a faecal material sample (poo) using the equipment provided	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>